

**PICTURES AT AN EXHIBITION BY M. P. MUSSORGSKY AS
PERCEIVED BY WESTERN AND RUSSIAN SCHOLARS**

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Summary

***Pictures at an Exhibition* by M. P. Mussorgsky as Perceived by
Western and Russian Scholars**

The article is devoted to Mussorgsky's famous a suite of pieces composed for piano, *Pictures at an Exhibition*. The author of this study examines, analyzes, and compares divergent perceptions of foreign and Russian scholars about this renowned composition by Mussorgsky. Due to the fact that there is such an array of diverse viewpoints about *Pictures at an Exhibition*, some of which are conflicting or even contradictory, there is a need to collect, expose, and discuss these findings. The purpose of this study, therefore, is to come to a better understanding of the meaning of Mussorgsky's composition through a thorough examination of various insights presented by numerous researchers. These discoveries, shared by Western and Russian scholars, will then add to the knowledge of musicologists and performers. Besides, this study introduces viewpoints and ideas expressed by Western scholars from sources that are less known in Eastern Europe.

Key words: Mussorgsky, *Pictures at an Exhibition*, suite of pieces composed for piano, miniatures for piano, Promenade, The Gnome, The Old Castle, The Tuileries, The Ox-Cart /Bydlo, Ballet of Unhatched Chicken Samuel Goldenberg and Schmuyle, The Market Place in Limoges, The Catacombs, The Hut on Hen Legs/Baba-Yaga, The Great Gate (Bogatyr Gates) of Kiev.

Rezumat

**„Tablouri dintr-o expoziție” de M. P. Musorgski
în percepția cercetătorilor occidentali și ruși**

Articolul este consacrat celebrului ciclu de piese cu program pentru pian „Tablouri dintr-o expoziție” de Musorgski. Autorul acestui articol investighează, analizează și compară percepțiile divergente ale cercetătorilor ruși și străini despre această lucrare renumită a lui Musorgski. Datorită faptului că există o asemenea varietate de puncte de vedere diferite cu privire la „Tablouri dintr-o expoziție”, dintre care unele sunt îndoielnice și chiar contradictorii, este necesar să se colecteze, să se analizeze și să se discute aceste afirmații. Scopul acestui studiu este, prin urmare, de a pătrunde mai bine în conceptul lucrării lui Musorgski, studiind cu atenție diferitele percepții prezentate de numeroși cercetători ai operei lui. Aceste descoperiri, împărtășite de oamenii de știință occidentali și ruși, vor adăuga apoi la cunoștințele muzicologilor și interpreților. În plus, acest articol prezintă cititorului cercetările occidentale, colectate din surse mai puțin cunoscute în Europa de Est.

Cuvinte-cheie: Musorgski, „Tablouri dintr-o expoziție”, ciclu de piese cu program, miniaturi pentru pian, Promenade, Gnomus, Castel vechi, Grădina Tuilerie, Bydlo, Baletul puilor neclozați, Doi evrei, bogătașul și săracul, Piața din Limoges, Catacombe, Baba Hârca/ BabaYaga, Porțile voinicești din Kiev.

Western and Russian researchers who have studied Mussorgsky's *Pictures at an Exhibition* have brought to light many interesting insights and perceptions about the cycle. These findings have to do with various aspects of the suite, such as: the interrelationship between Hartmann's paintings and Mussorgsky musical representations, dramatic significance of the suite, programmatic content of the pieces, analysis of the form, and interpretation of the titles. There is a significant difference

between Western and Russian perceptions about the cycle. Russian scholars, for instance, express deeply emotional viewpoints. To a certain extent, they identify themselves with the characters presented in the *Pictures*. Western scholars, on the contrary, base their perceptions almost exclusively on the written source of an undoubted authority. Therefore, their ideas about this suite do not necessarily coincide with the traditional viewpoints offered by Russian researchers.

Promenade

In a letter to Stasov, Mussorgsky mentioned that "...his physiognomy peeps out ...through the intermezzos." [9, p. 291] Some researchers, therefore, interpret this comment literally rather than figuratively and attempt to find a vivid musical self-portrait of the composer in the *Promenades*. David Brown, for instance, states,

...Promenade brilliantly suggests him [Mussorgsky] walking purposefully into the room, though there is an ebb and flow in the phrasing that indicates that his gait is subject to constant slight irregularities, perhaps through momentary shifts of direction as he turns to give the pictures a preliminary survey. [2, p. 233]

Michael Russ opines that *Promenade* "...is a portrait of Mussorgsky, now of considerate bulk, shambling through the gallery" [11, p. 35].

Schnitke, on the contrary, suggests that *Promenade* is a sort of epigraph that bears an epic-national character and while listening to it one may clearly feel the essence of the Russian spirit [12, p. 330]. Another Russian researcher Houbov views the *Promenades* as "a chain of reflections" [6, p. 535]. His colleague Shlifshtein, in turn, states that the *Promenades* reveal Mussorgsky's understanding of Hartmann's paintings and the composer's inner feelings [15, 221]. The Russian commentators, thus, suggest that the *Promenade* is a spiritual message from the composer and not a self-portrait.

1. Gnomus

The first character piece of the cycle following the opening *Promenade* bears the Latin title *Gnomus*, 'the gnome.' It portrays, according to Oskar von Riesemann, a "...dwarf who waddles with awkward steps on his short, bandy legs; the grotesque jumps of the music, and the clumsy, crawling movements with which these are interspersed, are forcibly suggestive." [9, p. 291] This perception, though vivid, of the *Gnomus* does not begin to describe the character's inner feelings. Mussorgsky aspired to reveal through music his compassion and love for simple and unfortunate people. The composer concentrated his attention on complex psychological characters. An adept of musical truth, Mussorgsky closely followed Beethoven's idea of creating melodic lines that resemble the intonations of human speech. Consequently, Mussorgsky was perhaps not so much interested in literally drawing a caricature of the Gnome in music, but rather in sharing the emo-

tional suffering and pain of this wretched creature. According to Bobrovsky, Mussorgsky's Gnome is a deeply tragic character of an evil fate [1, p. 146].

Mussorgsky's Gnome is reminiscent of another dwarf, Alberich, from Wagner's opera *Das Rheingold*: a desperate creature and a loner who cannot find love. There might be, perhaps, a parallel between the Gnome and Mussorgsky himself. Possessing an enormous talent, Mussorgsky never had his own home; never had a soul mate that would stand next to him against the challenges, unhappiness and misfortunes of life. This great genius of the 19th century, who was neglected by his contemporaries, but became a source of inspiration for a number of significant composers in Russia and abroad, died alone in a hospital, and his last words told to a nurse were, "Everything is finished. Ah, how miserable I am" [13, p. 175].

2. Il vecchio castello

The Italian title of the second *Picture* of the cycle may be translated as 'the old castle.' According to Oskar von Riesemann, it represents "...an old tower of the Middle Ages, in front of which a minstrel sings his song, a long, unspeakably melancholy melody." [9, p. 291] Surprisingly, the two most divergent opinions regarding this *Picture* have to do with the musical value of this piece. Calvocoressi claims, "Musically *Pictures from an Exhibition* show Mussorgsky not at his best, perhaps, but certainly at his most characteristic state. The only complete failure is *Il vecchio castello*." [3, p. 174] Schnitke, on the contrary, states that "The 'Old castle' is Musorgsky's brilliant achievement in the genre of romantic ballade..." [12, p. 333] Schnitke also considers this composition a rare combination of creative finding and inspiration, logically organized into a sophisticated form, which combines elements of rondo, ritornello, and free variations [12, p. 333].

In comparison to the Gnome's personal drama, his burning anger and desire for revenge, *Il vecchio castello* takes the listeners back in time and creates an atmosphere of melancholic solitude. While listening to music of *The Old Castle* listeners may imagine mysterious ruins that silently keep their dark secrets.

3. Tuileries (*Dispute d'enfants après jeux*)

The French title of this beautiful piece may be translated as, 'Tuileries (children quarrelling after play).' There are several different opinions

regarding Hartmann's illustration associated with this piece. For instance, Oscar von Riesemann states: "...Hartmann's picture shows a walk in the Tuileries gardens in Paris, crowded with playing children and their nurses" [9, p. 291]. Houbov expresses the same idea [6, p. 536]. Russ, on the contrary, claims that the illustration of the Tuileries gardens has vanished. [11, p. 38] Seroff, in turn, suggests that this *Picture* is "...Moussorgsky's free development of Hartmann's pencil drawing of one corner of a garden, deserted, and without children" [13, p. 143].

Even though there is no correlative drawing by Hartmann available, Mussorgsky's music is certainly visually evocative. One may imagine a scene in a famous Parisian garden where young children are arguing at play.

Schnittke claims that due to specific melodic intonations and plagal harmonies the music of the *Tuileries* sounds Russian. [12, p. 338] Houbov, in turn insists that in spite of Mussorgsky's French setting for this *Picture*, the action rather takes place in the famous *Letnii Sad* (Summer Garden) in St. Petersburg, and the children in the argument are not French but Russian [6, p. 537].

4. *Bydlo*

In his letter to Stasov, Mussorgsky wrote, "No 4. right between the eyes 'Sandomirzsko bydlo' (le télégue) [the cart] (le télégue, of course, is not named in the title, just between us)" [10, p. 302]. The final version of the title of this *Picture*, however, is not "Sandomirzsko Bydlo," but just *Bydlo*. The word "bydlo" translates from Russian as "rabble" and according to Lopouhov, "...it is one of the offensive names for the Russian peasantry." [7, p. 139] At the time when Mussorgsky was composing his suite, truthful observations about the horrible life of the serfs were neither welcomed nor encouraged by the monarchical authorities. The composer, therefore, had to express his thoughts and emotions through symbols and metaphors. Because the composer mentioned the word "le télégue" (the cart) in his letter, Stasov (in his program notes to the first edition of the *Pictures*) suggested that this piece is about a huge peasant dray on enormous wheels driven by oxen [9, p. 291]. Therefore, in some of the western scores this *Picture* is simply named *Polish Ox-Cart*. Mussorgsky, however, being a progressive composer, longed to reveal the social problems and psychological dramas of the Russian people through his art. He fo-

cused all of his compositional strength on depicting the enormous suffering of the poor, desperate, and oppressed Russian peasants [14, p. 84]. Therefore, *Bydlo* goes far beyond the naturalistic imitation of the wooden cart and the oxen that pulled it.

5. *Ballet of the Chicks in Their Shells*

According to Houbov, Mussorgsky composed this *Picture* having been inspired by Hartmann's illustration of a chick costume designed by Victor Hartmann for the ballet *Trilby* [6, p. 538]. Marius Petipa created this ballet for the St. Petersburg Imperial Theater in 1870. The plot of this ballet was based upon Charles Nodier's novel *Trilby, ou le Lutin d'Argail* [11, p. 41].

The researchers identify this *Picture* as a Scherzino. Oscar von Riesemann calls it a "... 'Scherzino' of the greatest charm" [9, p. 292]. Lopouhov defines this piece as a scherzino-humoresque. [7, p. 141] Schnittke identifies it as masterful and tasteful miniature [12, p. 340]. Schnittke suggests that Mussorgsky tried to reproduce the embryonic life of the unhatched chicks through his music [12, p. 340]. Lopouhov, however, claims that the chicks do come out of their shells in order to perform their ballet dance [7, p. 140-141].

Even though the researchers may disagree on whether Mussorgsky intended to reproduce the embryonic life of the chicks in their shells or picture their first steps into the world, the composer's unparalleled fantasy never cease to surprise the researchers, the performers, and the audiences.

6. *Two Polish Jews; One Rich, the Other Poor (Samuel Goldenberg and Schmuyle)*

In 1868, while traveling through Poland, Hartmann drew the portraits of two Jewish men from the small town of Sandomir [6, p. 538]. One of these men was rich and the other poor. In Hartmann's paintings the rich man looks self-assured, proud, and full of dignity. The poor man, on the contrary, looks feeble and frail. He dejectedly sits in the street wearing rags with his head hung low, holding nothing but a stick in his hands. Upon his return to Russia, Hartmann gave both of these drawings to Mussorgsky because the latter liked them very much [6, p. 538].

There are two different perceptions about the psychological meaning and content of this piece. Western and Russian scholars could be divided in two groups: one group claims that this piece is a caricature or a grotesquerie. The other, rath-

er merciful, group states that this piece is about a personal tragedy that reveals a deep social drama. The musical intonations attributed to the poor Schmuyle, however, imply that he should be taken seriously because he, being placed in unfortunate circumstances aggravated by the rich man's mistreatment, sorrowfully appeals for compassion rather than laughter.

7. *The Market Place in Limoges*

Mussorgsky left two program notes written in French, in which he described in details the events depicted in this piece. One of them reads in translation, "The great news: Monsier Pimpant de Pantapantaléon has just recovered his lost cow, the Fugitive. 'Yes, Maam, that was yesterday. – No, Maam, it was the day before yesterday. – Oh, well, Maam, the beast roamed all over the neighborhood. – Oh, no, Maam, the beast never got loose at all'" [4].

Riesemann truly states this piece is a "study in intonation" [9, p. 292]. Indeed, the composer, once again, masterfully imitated human voices, calls, shouts, and the intonations of speech. Montague-Nathan, on the contrary, made a doubtful comment about several *Pictures* of the suite, including *Limoges*, "The Spanish picture, the Tuileries scene, and 'Limoges,' are somewhat too formal for their purpose..." This comment is rather out of context because there is not a single Spanish *Picture* in the cycle. Also it is unclear by what criteria *Tuileries* and *Limoges* were identified as too formal. Both of these character pieces vividly depict scenes from everyday French life; *Tuileries* is a lyrical and subtle miniature, and *Limoges* vividly depicts an agitated crowd where quarrelling women are teasing each other.

8. *Catacombae (sepulcrum Romanum)*

In his drawing Hartmann represented three men exploring the catacombs. According to Russ, one of these men is Hartmann, another is Hartmann's colleague, and the third man is their guide [11, p. 45]. The right corner of this drawing shows a niche full of human skulls. Mussorgsky divided his musical *Picture* into two parts and gave them the following Latin titles: *sepulcrum Romanum*, 'the Roman tomb' and *Con mortuis in lingua mortua*, 'with the dead in the dead language.' The composer also added a program note, which reads: "The following text should be in Latin: the creative spirit of the late Hartmann leads me to the skulls, appeals to them; the skulls begin to gleam faintly" [10, p.

304] Upon reading these notes one may assume that Mussorgsky was greatly affected by the death of his beloved friend. The emotional wound was still fresh, and perhaps, the composer felt a mysterious spiritual connection with the late Hartmann.

There are several divergent perceptions about this piece. For instance, Montague-Nathan simply states, "...'The Catacombs' is a curiously fantastic number, part of which is based on the 'Promenade' theme" [8, p. 80]. Shirinian, on the contrary, suggests that *Catacombae* is an intimate philosophical reflection about life and death [14, p. 85]. Brown speculates that the beginning of this *Picture* is reminiscent of the *Prelude* from *Tristan und Isolde*, "Musorgsky now unceremoniously parodying Wagner's yearning for the most exquisite of physical pleasures in order to lay bare an experience of irrational terror that subsides with only painful slowness" [2, p. 239]. This deduction is a bit of a stretch because in this *Picture* Mussorgsky expresses his deep emotional grief for the dear friend he has just lost. Musically (aside from the slow tempo) there is no trace of melodic or harmonic connection between *The Catacombs* and the *Prelude* to *Tristan und Isolde*.

9. *The Hut on Fowl's Legs (Baba-Yaga)*

Hartmann's sketch includes a clock in the shape of a wooden hut that looks like a masterpiece of the carpenter's craft. Western and Russian researchers have different perceptions about this piece. The major disagreement lies in whether Mussorgsky was truly emulating Hartmann's drawing. For instance, Brown and Russ incorporate Hartmann's design of the clock into their description of the musical *Picture*. According to Brown, "...the witch's pendulum begins the frantic ticking that determines the pace of her ride" [2, p. 240]. Russ is even more specific; he states, "If the metronome marking is correct, then the indication ♩=120 leaves each bar with a duration of exactly one second; this, and the mechanical rhythm, gives the impression of a giant clock" [11, p. 47]. Russian researchers, on the contrary, question the idea of Mussorgsky incorporating the object from Hartmann's sketch into his *Picture*. Shirinian, for example, states that Hartmann's image of the clock in the shape of the stylized Russian hut inspired Mussorgsky to compose a fantastic musical piece picturing Baba-Yaga's ride in the mortar [14, p. 85]. Shlifshtein suggests that the musical *Picture* is about Baba-Yaga, her fren-

zied flight, and her mysterious magic spells [15, p. 218]. According to Trembovelsky, Hartmann's design of the clock does not imply such wild and dynamic music [17, p. 322]. Houbov, in his turn, states that the image from Hartmann's fine watercolor got transformed in Mussorgsky's mind into a vast and fantastic story about Baba-Yaga [6, p. 542]. Therefore, according to Russian scholars, Hartmann's sketch gave Mussorgsky an impulse and inspired him to create a musical fantasy about Baba-Yaga, but not about the clock or the hut.

10. *The Great Gate of Kiev*

Hartmann's sketch of the gate represents a very unusual and asymmetric architectonic structure designed in an Old Russian style. It consists of three massive arches and a bell tower. According to Seroff, "Moussorgsky's last picture in his piano suite has nothing photographically resembling Hartmann's design for the great Gate of Kiev..." [13, 143]. Schnittke, on the contrary, claims that musical representation of the *Great Gate* came closer than ever to Hartmann's original drawing; the massive chords symbolize the pillars, the church-like design inspired Mussorgsky to introduce the church chant, and the image of the bell tower resulted in the impressive church bell pealing in this musical *Picture* [12, 352]. Brown points out that "casual observers" depicted in Hartmann's watercolor become "human participants" in Mussorgsky's piece [2, 240]. Houbov states that Hartmann's design inspired Mussorgsky to represent in music Russian knight-hood that is praised in numerous Russian legends [6, 544]. The folk-like intonations that are present in the music of *The Great Gate* are similar to those previously heard in the *Promenades*. According to Schnittke, everything that symbolized Russian spirit throughout the cycle becomes concentrated in *The Great Gate of Kiev* [12, 357]. Indeed, old Russia associates with its heroes' might, their willingness to sacrifice their lives for the native land, pride for the nation, patriotism, faith in God and church, predilection for mass festivities, and the people's devotion to their tsar. In his final *Picture* Mussorgsky created an apotheosis, an elaborate scene that represents his beloved Russia in its splendor and grandeur.

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